

NEWSLETTER

Allergy Cancer BioNano Research Centre

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January – June 2021

Welcome to our second, virus-free newsletter!

The ACBN Research Centre keeps developing, with the groups of Nicole Meisner-Kober and Andreas Uhl joining with the start of 2021 and with the group of Chiara Cabrele leaving. You will find portraits of the new groups in future editions.

As an update, the move from Billrothstrasse to the NaWi has not yet happened and we will keep you informed – see the story in the first newsletter.

In this edition you will find:

- ❖ an update from Fritz Aberger, Head of the Department of Biological Sciences, on **changes in the organization of the University** that are relevant for us,
- ❖ an overview on **particle and nano-sciences** undertaken within ACBN both at the NaWi and in Itzling, as well as
- ❖ a portrait of the **group of Iris Gratz** and their research on immunity.

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A fresh breeze at PLUS – A glimpse into the future through the lens of the Department of Biosciences

Since October 2019, the Paris Lodron University of Salzburg (PLUS) has been steered by a new rectorate. Rector Lehnert and his team have set themselves the goal of giving the university and its organizational units clear and modern profiles and creating synergies to become even more visible and successful in national and international competition. This is without doubt of high importance and priority in a future-oriented, innovative university landscape.

To this end, starting in 2022, there will be new faculties and departments at PLUS, which in the future will be much more visible and even more dedicated to the priority topics and global challenges of our society, such as digitalization, climate change and human health. The current Faculty of Natural Sciences will reorganize into a Faculty of Digital and Analytical Sciences and a Faculty of Natural and Life Sciences. The Department of Biosciences - currently by far the largest organizational unit at PLUS - is also undergoing a profile-boosting reorganization to become a department with a new name: *Biosciences & Medical Biology*.

However, the real task and actual challenge to be mastered now concerns the successful implementation of the profile-raising reorganization measures, which for the time being have been decided and outlined on paper, only.

*the more
things change,
the more they
remain the same*

Jean-Baptiste Alphonse Karr

So what is required for a successful reorganization process, and what do we need to emphasize and focus on in particular? First and foremost, it always comes down to the people. It will be critical to pick up the many hard- and successfully working colleagues and to inspire them for the common journey into the future, to inspire them for more collaborative work and common topics without leaving behind the existing expertise and competence of the individual and to secure freedoms while still paying attention to added value and synergies in a collaboration network with critical mass. Furthermore, it will require a strong push for investments into cutting-edge technologies to have new tools at hand that enable excellent research at the pulse of time. For sure we agree that without the best infrastructure it will not be possible for even the smartest and best minds to be successful in the long term.

And finally, a well thought-out and broadly supported concept is needed to attract young and outstanding scientists with new ideas and complementary skills to PLUS through targeted and intelligent recruitments where expertise is lacking. All of this requires a certain intuition to find the right dose of renewal and preservation of successful, established areas. In other words, one should remember what life can teach us: *"the more things change, the more they remain the same"* (Jean-Baptiste Alphonse Karr). The right mix and the appropriate dosage will thus contribute significantly to the successful further development of both the new Department of Biosciences & Medical Biology and ACBN. *Competence for tomorrow* is the new PLUS motto. Let's get to work!

Fritz Aberger

Fritz Aberger

Bio-Nano Interactions at ACBN

The field of Bio-Nano Interaction (BNI) sciences is one of the three major pillars of the ACBN Research Centre. Research in BNI has evolved as a stand-alone field located at the interface between chemistry and physics of materials, biotechnology, and medicine. Within the ACBN, it is well connected to the areas of allergy and cancer, as nanomaterials bear big hopes in diagnosis and therapy of allergic disease and cancer.

In the department of Chemistry and Physics of Materials in Itzling Milena Schenck, under the supervision of Andrea Feinle and Nicola Hüsing, is working on multifunctional nanoparticle based delivery systems. Particles are designed and engineered according to the needs of the respective biomedical application. Attaching the drug to a particle can result in the alteration of the uptake pathway, enables the active targeting and drug release at specific cells or tissues and allows easy tracking by fluorescent labelling ([Scheiblhofer et al. 2016](#)). The particle systems were developed based on a surface functionalized silica core where targeting compounds and the drug can be covalently bound or attached by electrostatic interactions. Alternatively, a nanocapsule has been prepared based on tannic acid polypeptide interactions where the drug is incorporated within the capsule. In ongoing cooperation, particles have been developed for the targeting of dendritic cells and the specific delivery of particle bound antigens (in cooperation with Richard Weiss) and the *in vivo* tracking of the immune suppressive drug rapamycin in lymph nodes (in cooperation with Iris Gratz).

Structural alterations of proteins can take place when they bind onto nanoparticle surfaces and this non-covalent interaction is having consequence on their biological behavior. Building on the strong expertise in the field of molecular allergology within ACBN, we apply natural extracts and recombinant allergens as models for a better understanding of such consequences, in particular in regard to immunological endpoints. Recently, we sought to align *in vitro* experimentation of protein corona formation, the event when particles due to their high surface energy spontaneously become coated with biomolecules, with *in silico* prediction approaches.

Key questions here are: Can proteins bind selectively to nanoparticles? Do proteins bind in randomized orientation or can they adopt preferred orientations at the particle surface? What are the biological consequences? Can we model the BNI process of protein corona formation by *in silico* tools? How does the nanotopography of the particle surface impact these BNI? These and other questions are pursued by Ingrid Hasenkopf, Litty Johnson, and Robert Mills-Goodlet based on funding by ICA (FWF: W01213) and [NanoCommons](#) (EC H2020: 731032).

Uptake of nanoparticles into lung epithelial cells and investigation of their potential function as delivery vehicles for proteins, in particular allergens, such as the major birch pollen allergen Bet v 1 ([Johnson et al., 2020](#)). Here, we apply most realistic conditions for testing BNI at the respiratory barrier by culturing cells at the air-liquid interface ([Mills-Goodlet et al., 2020](#)). To achieve most realistic exposure conditions for testing nanomedical applications, the NAVETTA aerosol exposure chamber, patented by the BNI research group, will be installed in the new BS-2 facility in near future.

Human lung cells containing Bet v 1-conjugated SiO₂ nanoparticles

In addition to the study of BNI and uptake of protein-nanoparticle conjugates into human epithelial and immune cells, ACBN has been conducting projects on mixture toxicity of nanoparticles with bystander substances. In 2017, Martin Himly and Mark Geppert launched the Sparkling Science project "[Nan-O-Style](#)" (SPA06/270), which aimed to investigate the interaction of nanoparticles with ingredients from modern lifestyle products (e.g., cosmetics) and their resulting mixture toxicities on human skin cells. Furthermore, Nan-O-Style initiated an Austrian-wide survey on the perception and knowledge on nanotechnology in the Austrian population. During the entire project, students from different high schools all over Austria were extensively involved in the research. Three students performed internships in our lab ("Talentpraktikum", FFG: 870755 and 874754), all of them were awarded to be part of the Top 20 all over Austria.

The project resulted in two scientific publications by the ACBN researchers ([Joubert et al., 2019](#); [Geppert et al., 2020](#)) and more than a dozen of peer-reviewed articles by the school students in the [Open Schools Journal](#) for Open Science.

Larisa Manaj during her FFG Talentpraktikum

Milena Schenck

Andrea Feinle

Mark Geppert

Martin Himly

Investigation of interactions of nanoparticles with bystander substances will be continued in the – just recently accepted – project **PUSH (The PLUS-UP European-African university network for sustainable innovation and health)** by Mark Geppert, Martin Himly and Ndeke Musee. Main research goal for this project is to elucidate mixture effects of nanoparticles and emerging contaminants in the environment on different levels: bacteria, environmental organisms, and human health. PUSH is a joint project of PLUS and the University of Pretoria (South Africa). Aside from research, it also involves joint teaching events to bring the fields of ecotoxicology, nanotechnology and nanomedicine closer together. The project will start in summer 2021 and endure for 2 years.

These endeavors in nanosafety assessment are recognized well at international level. The success story was mainly driven by Albert Duschl, who, over the past decades, actively participated in four framework programmes of the European Commission (EC) on themes ranging from particle toxicology to nanosafety. Martin Himly chairs the [Working Group A on Education, Training and Communication of the EU Nanosafety Cluster](#) coordinating educational activities of all EC-funded projects in safety aspects of nanotechnology-enabled products, advanced & smart materials, nanomedicine, and beyond. In line with this, Sabine Hofer, Norbert Hofstätter, Martin Himly, and Albert Duschl contribute to risk governance in nanotechnology ([NanoRigo](#), EC H2020: 814530) and overall the ACBN, thus, helps to promote so-called safe-and-sustainable-by-design (SSbD) approaches for innovation and development.

List of cited publications

Johnson et al., 2020, Vaccines,
<https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines8020237>

Mills-Goodlet et al., 2020, Environ. Sci. Nano,
<https://doi.org/10.1039/C9EN01353A>

Joubert et al., 2019, Nanoimpact,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.impact.2019.100201>

Geppert et al., 2020, Chem Res & Toxicol,
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrestox.9b00428>

*Milena Schenck, Andrea Feinle,
Mark Geppert, Martin Himly*

The Tissue Immune Regulation group

Meet our Research group

Iris Gratz moved from the University of California, San Francisco (UCSF) to Salzburg to join the PLUS and start the Immune Regulation Group in March 2014. The group was then invited to join ACBN (then Biosciences and Health).

Within ACBN we are supporting other groups with our expertise in animal science and collaborate on projects related to tumor immunology. Overall, the principal goal of our research is to investigate the mechanisms of immune regulation in peripheral tissues such as the skin. We aim to elucidate mechanisms of immune regulation in inflammatory settings using novel and unique (humanized) mouse models of tissue (auto)immunity. Additionally, we develop approaches to manipulate immune responses *in vivo* and apply these to various clinically relevant inflammatory settings such as skin grafting and wound healing. In summary, we aim to understand basic mechanisms of tissue immune regulation and inflammation with the goal to lay the groundwork for novel therapeutic strategies to treat chronic and debilitating inflammatory skin conditions.

The Team and our Research Projects

Skin is a crucial barrier of the body against pathogenic invaders and is thus rich in immune cells. Our group aims to understand the role of various cutaneous immune cells and their cross-talk with skin stromal cells in skin autoimmunity, wound healing and cancer. The specific projects and involved researchers are described in the text.

From 2006 - 2009, Iris Gratz was a Postdoc at the [EB House Austria](#), a Centre of Expertise for Epidermolysis Bullosa (EB) and Special Clinic for "Butterfly Children", a group of patients that suffer from a rare genetic condition in which the skin blisters very easily. Since then, she was always fascinated by this patient group and the team is still working towards elucidating several aspects of the **Immunology of Epidermolysis Bullosa**. In collaboration with the team of the EB House Austria, Anshu Sharma and Katharina Umundum analyze the immunological consequences of skin gene therapy of EB patients (to replace mutated genes that are essential for dermal-epidermal integrity). Additionally, they also study the role of skin-tropic immune cells in the regulation of skin wound healing and cancer development. (funding Debra Austria)

Cutaneous Tissue-resident memory T cells (T_{RM}) persist locally in the skin where they provide frontline defense against recurring insults. We have recently found that a fraction of these skin T_{RM} cells can exit the tissue and be identified as a novel population of skin-tropic CLA^+CD4^+ T cells in the peripheral blood. These cells have a regulatory phenotype and likely participate in host-protective antimicrobial and wound healing responses following tissue damage. In this project, Suraj Varkhande and Leonie Schöftner work in close collaboration with the group of Daniel J. Campbell at the Benaroya Research Institute in Seattle, WA, USA. Together, we use *in vitro* analyses, skin organoids and innovative humanized mouse models to assess the function of human T_{RM} during cutaneous inflammation and wound healing. (funding NIH)

In addition to the aforementioned skin T_{RM} cells, **Cutaneous Gamma Delta T cells** (specifically $V\delta 1^+$ T cells) have unique functions in the skin and play a central role in defense against cutaneous tumors. Together with [GammaDelta Therapeutics](#), Giorgia Nasi studies the biology of human cutaneous $V\delta 1^+$ T cells in skin-humanized mice. In this project we take advantage of the proprietary isolation and expansion protocols developed by GammaDelta Therapeutics to selectively generate $V\delta 1^+$ T cell populations suitable for clinical application. Additionally, Giorgia is interested in the role of cutaneous $\gamma\delta$ T cells in the etiology of Epidermolysis Bullosa. (funding GammaDelta Therapeutics)

In barrier tissues such as the skin the decision between immune activation in response to pathogens versus tolerance is determined by the balance between suppressive regulatory T cells (Treg) and pro-inflammatory effector T cells (Teff). In addition to thymic Treg (tTreg) cells, peripherally generated Treg (pTreg) cells are crucial in regulating the response to innocuous antigens such as skin-specific self-antigens and commensals.

Iris Gratz

Image references:

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Together with seven research groups from Vienna we test the hypothesis that histone deacetylases (HDACs) regulate the differentiation and function of T cells. Within the FWF-funded [SFB-F70](#) Gertrude Achatz, Alice Taliento and Melanie Lietzenmayer focus on the **role of HDACs in the generation of peripheral regulatory T cells**.

Specifically, we study the role of class I HDACs in pTreg generation, function and migration to the skin utilizing an experimental model for T cell-mediated skin autoimmune inflammation. With our research we support the overall aim of the SFB research program and consortium to provide an immunological and molecular rationale for using sub-class-specific and isoform-selective HDAC inhibitors in the treatment of T cell-mediated diseases. (funding FWF programs ICA and SFB-70 HIT)

We are looking forward to continuing our collaborations within ACBN and beyond and we are inviting students to apply for Master's positions within our group.

*The Immune Regulation Team
Headed by Iris Gratz*

In 2020, ACBN faculty members (PIs and mid-level staff) published 116 manuscripts, including 95 articles in specialist journals and 9 reviews. A total of 12 new research projects were awarded to ACBN members in 2020. The donors were the FWF, the European Union, DEBRA Austria, the Austrian Diabetes Society, the State of Salzburg, the European Directorate for Quality of Medicines and Healthcare, Austrian Academic Exchange Service (ÖAD) as well as several pharmaceutical companies. The total amount raised was € 2,158,452.

We wish you a successful and healthy time, take care!